

chambers are twice as deep as the main tank and always contain water. They are connected by "T" pieces that direct the water flow from the top of one chamber to the bottom of the next. If significant numbers of the nematodes survive successive sedimentation, they can be killed by adding formaldehyde to the chambers. Water leaving the last sedimentation chamber is directed into

an open drain with an independent water supply, which may be used to dilute any chemical treatment.

In 1979, a successful infestation was achieved in a plot (8 X 8 m) by incorporating 1.5 infested panicles/m² with the surface soil at sowing in early April; the subsequent rice crop was almost totally lost because of ufra.

Miniature deepwater tanks (IRRN 4:3), which provide total exclusion, or polythene cages, which prevent the mass movement of nematodes between adjacent plots, may be used to segregate individual plots from water in the main tank. The main tank can also be used to study other methods of ufra control such as transplanting. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Cold tolerance

Effect of low temperature on boro rice in West Bengal

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The dry season (boro) rice crop on the Gangetic Plains of West Bengal is subject to low-temperature stress, which inhibits normal plant growth and delays maturity (av min day/night temperature is 25.2/9.2°C – 28.8/14.9°C). The possibility of minimizing the effect of cold by using tolerant varieties and modified agronomic practices was investigated at the Chinsurah RRS.

The more important results are summarized:

- When seeds are sown on 12 November, 26 November, and 10 December (the traditional sowing time), seedling height gradually decreases, regardless of variety, as temperature falls (av min 17.4–9.7°C). But seedlings sown in mid-November have the proper height and higher dry-matter content at 45 days after sowing. That facilitates transplanting.

- Low temperature delays seedling leaf emergence by as long as 30 days. As seedlings grow older, the effect of low temperature disappears; regardless of variety and sowing time, the 4-leaf stage occurs at 45 days after sowing.

- Seedlings sown in mid-November (25.5/9.6°C – 29.0/14.4°C) have higher ultimate plant height and number of

fertile tillers than seedlings sown in early December.

- The crop sown in early December has a shorter growth duration than that sown earlier. Early flowering causes high spikelet sterility. Seed fertility is higher under a diurnal temperature range of 31.5/20.1°C – 33.5/22.4°C during panicle initiation to flowering, which occurs in the second week of March, regardless of variety or sowing date.

- Mid-November sowing gives higher yields for all the varieties. Yields of crops sown on 26 November and 10 December were 22 and 30% lower, respectively.

- Among several high yielding varieties tested, CR126-42-1 showed the best general adaptability for boro. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Influence of insecticide sprays on brown planthopper resurgence

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An IRR1 experiment was conducted to determine the effect of the last insecticide in a series of three spray applications in inducing BPH resurgence.

Ten-day-old TN1 seedlings were planted at 2 seedlings/pot in clay pots 12 cm in diameter. The potted plants

were kept insect free. Sprays were prepared in water from commercial formulations of emulsifiable concentrates at 0.04% concentration (except decamethrin, for which 0.002% was used). The quantity of spray fluid required per plot – at 500 liters/ha – was based on field recommendations.

Ten days after planting, the first insecticide was sprayed. The potted plants were placed on an electrically operated revolving table and the insecticide was sprayed with an atomizer. The plants were sprayed either three times with the same insecticide or one or

two times with one insecticide followed by another insecticide. The plants in each pot were covered with cylindrical mylar film cages and were maintained in an insectary with a regulated temperature of 27 ± 1°C, relative humidity of 60–80%, and photoperiod of 12 hours/day.

Fifteen days after the 3d spraying, 2 gravid BPH females/pot were released and confined with the sprayed plants for 7 days. Sufficient populations of test insects of the same age were maintained on TN1 plants to daily replace dead insects. After 7 days, the insects were